
INTERACTIVE TEACHING METHODS IN CONTEMPORARY HIGHER EDUCATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7353558>

Sagatova Muborak Payzidinovna

Senior lecturer of the department of foreign languages
Journalism and Mass Communication University of Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT

This article deals with the issue of the main strategy of modern education that should focus on the student's independent activity, the organization of self-learning environments and experimental and practical training, where students have a choice of actions and can use initiative—as well as flexible training programs where students can work in a comfortable rhythm.

Keywords: *flexibility, knowledge, motivation, interactive method, competence, ability.*

Today, we should talk about the use of interactive methods of training, which encourage interest in the profession; promote the efficient acquisition of training material; form patterns of conduct; provide high motivation, strength, knowledge, team spirit and freedom of expression; and most importantly, contribute to the complex competences of future specialists. The training, case study, behavioural modelling, peer feedback, play project, metaphor game, storytelling, basket and action learning methods—and their potential in professional training—are briefly described.

Competence-based approach in the system of higher is intended to increase attention to the effective and technological formation of professional competences. Professional competence we understand as a personal education that determines the productivity of professional tasks and includes knowledge, skills and professionally significant personal qualities, experiences and value orientations. In this case, competence differs from such traditional concepts as “knowledge”, “ability”, “skills” and “experience” by its integrative nature, determined by personal traits, such as practice-oriented focus, the ability to work in a wide variety of contexts, self-regulation and self-esteem.

Such a definition of professional competence requires significant changes in the pedagogical support of the university curriculum, filling it with teaching methods which could provide the training of future specialists with the required comprehensive result. The traditional methods of the university educational process (lecture, explanation, exercise, etc.) are certainly important for professional development. However, their limitations are felt even more acutely at present when a complex phenomenon such as competence is formed. Therefore, we believe that modern education should focus on the student's independent activity, the organization of self-learning environments and experimental and practical training, where students have a choice of actions and can use initiative—as well as flexible training programs where students can work in a comfortable rhythm.

Training is a teaching method that aims at developing skills and knowledge in any field by performing sequential tasks, activities or games. This method allows the teacher to give the participants missing information and allows students to form skills of professional and appropriate behaviour in the performance of professional tasks. The advantage of training is that it ensures the active involvement of all students in the process of training.

Discover – This step is a necessary procedure for the first class of any training. It activates the group for engaging in interaction and developing communication skills. It should be done even if the students know each other already. Through games such as “interview”, “Know Me” and “exchange of business cards”, participants can see a new side of and feel concern for each other.

Expectations of the participants - Participants' expectations are clarified—for example, “in a circle”—with the help of the training issues that they meet at the time. Addressing the needs of the student not only directs their interest but is also an important benchmark for the activities of the teacher.

Determination of the order of the training - When all of the participants talk or write about their expectations, the teacher always tells them the training procedure, regardless of how long it lasts.

Adoption of the rules of the group (the “agreement”) - For the participants to feel responsible for their training from the very beginning it is recommended that they accept the rules of the training or make an “agreement”. The articles of the agreement are usually recorded: e.g., we do not come late, speak out of turn, listen to off-topic conversation, etc. Each article is discussed, approved by majority vote and displayed in an accessible place. It will help create an appropriate working

atmosphere, mutual respect and trust. It also needs to improve the learning of the material. Every student is responsible for the execution of the “agreement”.

Assessment of group information level is one of the tasks for the teacher. A questionnaire or checklist with the questions on the training theme are usually used for this purpose. Polling results show the level of students' readiness and help the teacher correct the content and balance of the topics, adapt the training and make the exercises easy to understand. A questionnaire repeated after the training is over is very effective. Comparing the results, the teacher will be able to assess how students increased their readiness, which is an important measure of training efficiency.

Actualization of the problem. To develop the motivation for modifying professional behaviour and activity, the participants should be encouraged to discuss the training theme to arouse interest and make this issue relevant to everyone. The teacher can do a role play in the end.

Education. Direct interaction between teacher and students is to implement the key goal of the training at this stage. This stage of training involves two steps. The first one is information: it can start with answering the items from the questionnaires which caused the most embarrassment. In addition, the main course material is presented at this stage by using such methods as lectures, talks, role playing, discussions and small group work. The second stage is practice-oriented: it is designed to help the participants acquire practical experience. Role playing, dramatization, discussion, “brainstorming” and other interactive forms of work can be used for this purpose.

Summing up. Typically, this procedure is designed to ensure that the participants share their impressions and feelings and express their wishes. Summing up can involve filling the “sheet of revelation,” letters, questionnaires or surveys. An important component of training is the documentation of the student's progress, e.g., via photography. While summing up, these photos can be viewed to remind how the work was proceeding.

Thus, training efficiently forms students' professional competence through establishing a confident and comfortable environment and the possibility of practically drilling the steps that are essential for future professional activities in general.

Case study method. The case study method is training by solving specific cases. The essence of this method is a collective analysis of a situation, finding a solution and a public defence of said solution. In the process of reviewing the cases,

students gain the skills of teamwork, independent modelling of the solution, independent reasoning and defending their opinion. The method was first applied at Harvard Law School University in 1870.

This method involves ambiguity in the solution of the presented problem, which creates a challenge for discussing the reasoning of proposed solutions and choosing the most appropriate one. Therefore, the result is not only knowledge but also professional skills and a well-formed personality and set of values.

REFERENCES

1. Kumar M. Agarwal Internet-Based Language Learning and Teaching, Riga Business School, Riga Technical University Skolas St. 11, Lv-1010, Riga, Latvia
2. Khasanova, G. K. (2022). THE NEED FOR TECHNOLOGY IN THE DESIGN OF THE PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(Special Issue 20), 95-100.
3. Khasanova, Gulsanam Khusanovna. "THE ESSENCE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE CASE-STUDY METHOD IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS." *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences* 2.Special Issue 20 (2022): 778-782.
4. Юлбарсова Х. А. (2020). КОММУНИКАТИВНАЯ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТЬ КАК НЕОБХОДИМАЯ СОСТАВЛЯЮЩАЯ ЛИЧНОСТИ БУДУЩЕГО УЧИТЕЛЯ. *Интернаука*, 23(152 часть 2), 54.